

FAMILY STABILITY AS PREDICTORS OF SELF-ESTEEM AMONG PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN AWKA EDUCATION ZONE, ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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<p>Key words: Economic Stability, Relationship Stability, Social Stability, Family Stability, Self-Esteem and Public Secondary Schools.</p>	<p>Abstract: <i>This study examined the predictive values of family stability on self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone, Anambra State, Nigeria. The following aspects of family stability were determined; Family Economic Stability, Family Social Stability and Family Relationship Stability. The study was guided by three research questions and three hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. Predictive Correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 13,538 students in 65 Public Secondary Schools in Awka Education Zone. Multi-stage random sampling procedure was used to draw a sample size of 1,265 students representing the entire population. A structured Family Stability Questionnaire (FSQ) and Self Esteem Questionnaire (SEQ) were used to collect data for the study. The instruments were validated by three experts in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria and the reliability to ascertain the consistency of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha reliability index which yielded an aggregate coefficient of 0.79 and 0.84 respectively and was considered fit for the study. The administration of the instrument was done through the direct method approach. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Regression Statistics were utilized for data analysis. The p-value was used to determine the predictive relationship of the variables at 0.05 level of significance for the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that family stability has a positive predictive value on self-esteem of students in Awka Education Zone. The study also revealed that the three aspects of family stability that were examined, significantly predict self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone, Anambra State, Nigeria. The study recommended among others, that the Parents, Guidance Counsellors should encourage the students to imbibe behaviours and attitudes in line with societal values and acceptable norms to help enhance their self-esteem.</i></p>
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Introduction

Education plays a crucial role in value creation and transformation of learners in becoming productive and resourceful members of the society. It also instructs and supports learners to become responsible members of the family members. Learning provides an opportunity for nurturing one's mind to possess a feeling of self-worth. Having self-worth and positive feelings give the individual confidence to pursue life. This personal confidence and self-worth can be referred to as self-esteem. Nwokolo and Oguzie (2021), defined self-esteem as the belief, perception and opinion people have about themselves which influence their behaviours and consequently affects their performance and achievements in life. Self-esteem can also be seen as an overall reflection of an individual's self-worth, which encompasses beliefs about the individual as well as emotional responses to those beliefs (Anyamene, Obi and Okpala, 2023). This means that self-esteem defines the belief, value and level of confidence the individual has for oneself. It expresses the feelings and self-worth of individuals.

Ersoy (2018), asserted that self-esteem is the attitude and overall evaluation of one's own worth, or evaluation of given traits, position in the group, own activities and relationships with others. Those higher in self-esteem have an inherently strong sense of worth, while those low in self-esteem can sometimes feel worthless and even dislike themselves. (Abdel-Khalek, 2016; Jordan, Zeigler-Hill, and Cameron, 2017). In other words, self-esteem is a crucial quality that equips today's students to embrace both glaring

opportunities and challenging situations with confidence. Strong self-esteem among students can also be linked to family stability.

Family stability can be seen as the extent of consistency and predictability of a family in providing support and security to the family members. Manuel (2023), asserted that family stability comprises not just the presence of both parents and a solid marriage relationship, but also consistent routines and a secure home environment. Manuel, further stressed that the significance of maintaining family stability has implications that transcend beyond the immediate well-being of children, impacting their overall development. Family stability promotes positive social behavior in children and adolescents, while instability is associated with social maladjustment, including behaviors such as aggression toward peers, teachers, or parents (Omori and Ajah, 2019). Children learn family values, attitudes and behaviours from their homes. In the research study of Briggs, Cantrell and Karberg (2019), findings showed that family stability was associated with children's lifestyle towards social competence. They were of the opinion that children whose parents were married at birth had higher social competence and lower aggression than those whose parents were cohabiting or not living with a partner. Many a time, these are influenced by their family economic stability, family social stability and family relationship stability (Edward, 2024).

Family economic stability takes care of the basic needs of the members of the family. Family economic stability defines the financial stability

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which enables families to access safe housing, healthy foods, and other necessities, to engage fully in their communities, and to plan for the future (Ascend, 2019). This is to say that, when students embrace provision of support for their education and overall well-being, it will help in building up confidence and self-esteem for pursuit of a career. Parents work hard to ensure adequate provision of demands at home to meet up with their established standard of living. The average income of the family determines their economic family status and also maintains the economic family stability. Therefore, provisions of family responsibilities become a priority to meet up with economic stability at home (Omori and Ajah, 2019). Family stability can also reflect on the social interaction of the children.

Family social stability enables the children to integrate smoothly in respect of societal values, acceptable attitudes and behaviours. Edward (2024), posited that family social stability ensures responsibility of teaching children the norms, values, and behaviors necessary for them to function as members of the society. Through this process, families transmit cultural traditions and societal expectations across generations, ensuring continuity and stability. Omoruyi (2014), observed that children in the society acquire initial education and socialization from parents while social perception on other significant activities are from the world outside the family. Family social stability provides conditions and circumstances which influence the child, physically, intellectually and emotionally. Within the family context, children gradually internalize social standards and expectations, a process that facilitates greater

self-regulation skills and responsibility for their own behaviours (Amadi and Segun, 2013). It can be noted that family social stability helps to nurture the children with family culture, integrating acceptable societal value, norms upon building courage that could boost self-esteem among the children.

More so, family relationship stability could have or may not have influence on self-esteem of students. It can be said that the family has unique characteristics and relationships compared to other instituted groups. Moloko, Keiichi and Shuhei (2016), opined family life relationship stability as coping family condition, the state of mind of the parents, the degree of family cohesiveness, family unity and interaction among the members of the family. Family relationship stability takes care of the members' relations, emotions, communication as well as psychological development which could contribute to the nurturing of self-esteem. Gross (2017) reveals that caring family is significantly related with family relationship stability, which enhances a child's self-worth and confidence. It is expected of a positive family relationship stability to confer multiple developmental assets for the children. This can come through caregiving, stable economic resources, socio-cultural norms, quality parenting and supervision which transforms into positive behavioural outcomes, self-worth and self-esteem.

Basically, self-esteem enables students to believe in their ability to learn, achieve and contribute to the world around them. Self-esteem is a frame of mind that allows us to celebrate strengths, challenge weaknesses and possess perseverance.

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Sadly, these strengths characterized by self-esteem are not really seen nor perceived among students in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. Ugwu and Nwokocha (2021) noted that self-esteem of secondary school students in this study area has been significantly affected by numerous factors and needed to be addressed. Nnadi, Oguzie, Okonkwo (2025), observed that students often exhibit signs of self-doubt, low self-confidence and increased vulnerability to negative peer influence and that concerned educators and stakeholders indicated a troubling trend of this low self-esteem among many secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Students' ability to develop a positive self-image in facing life situations has been of great concern to school administrators, counsellors, teachers, parents and guardians. Building up self confidence among students in schools, towards achieving their academic and personal goals are deemed worthwhile. Education stakeholders strive to enlighten the students through different programmes on the needs to build up courage to enhance their self-esteem. Despite their efforts, available literature and personal observations show that there is still a decline in self-esteem among students in Awka Education Zone, especially in public secondary schools. There are still feelings of self-doubt, social withdrawal, anxiety, lack of self-confidence and low self-motivation among the students. This low self-esteem has kept principals, counselors, teachers and other stakeholders worrisome.

It is expected that emotional regulation and stability, healthy and stronger relationships and resilience in the face of challenges should be

cultivated in the students through supportive family stability to help in building up students' self-esteem. This situation motivated the current study. The researcher therefore, seeks to examine family stability as predictors of self-esteem among students in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study determined family stability as predictors of self-esteem among students in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. Specifically, the study examined:

1. Predictive value of Family economic stability on self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.
2. Predictive value of Family social stability on self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.
3. Predictive value of Family relationship stability on self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the predictive value of family economic stability on the self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone?
2. What is the predictive value of family social stability on the self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone?
3. What is the predictive value of family relationship stability on the self-esteem of public secondary schools students in Awka Education Zone?

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Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant predictive value of family economic stability on the self-esteem of Public Secondary School Students in Awka Education Zone.
2. There is no significant predictive value of family social stability on the self-esteem of Public Secondary School Students in Awka Education Zone.
3. There is no significant predictive value of family relationship stability on the self-esteem of Public Secondary School Students in Awka Education Zone.

Methods

Correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 13,538 students in 65 Public Secondary Schools in Awka Education Zone. Multi-stage random sampling procedure was used to select 10% of the entire population comprising 1,360 students, representing the sample size of the study. Two sets of questionnaires were used for data collection. They are titled: Family Stability Questionnaire (FSQ) and Self Esteem Questionnaire (SEQ). The questionnaire has section A with background information and instructions. Section B is structured in Clusters with each item assigned a four-point scale of: Strongly Agree (SA); Agree (A); Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD), with corresponding

Table 1: Pearson (r) correlation analysis of the predictive value of family economic stability on the self-esteem of secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instruments were validated by experts in the field and considered fit for the study. The internal consistency of the items was obtained using Cronbach alpha which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.79 for family stability and 0.84 for self-esteem. The researcher administered the copies of the instrument directly to the respondents with the help of research research assistants. Out of the 815 copies administered to the respondents, a total of 782 copies representing 96% were properly completed, successfully retrieved and used for data analysis. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation coefficient (r) was used to answer the research questions while regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The coefficient (r) between 0.0 - 0.40 yielded a low predictive value, 0.41 - 0.60 yielded a moderate predictive value, 0.61 - 0.80 yielded a high predictive value and between 0.81 - 1.00 yielded a very high substantial predictive value. In testing the hypotheses the decision rules that when p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis were rejected. However, if the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Results

Research Question One. What is the predictive value of family economic stability on the self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone?

Variables	N	Family_Economic_Stability	Students' Self-esteem	Remarks
Family Economic Stability	1265	1.00	0.751	High Predictive Value
Students' Self-esteem	1265	0.751	1.00	

Results in Table 1 showed that Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of 0.751 was obtained. This coefficient is between 0.61 and 0.80 showing a high predictive value. This means that there is a high positive predictive value of family economic stability on students' self-esteem in

public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone.

Research Question Two. What is the predictive value of family social stability on the self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone?

Table 2: Pearson (r) correlation analysis of the predictive value of family social stability on the self-esteem of secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Variables	N	Family_Social_Stability	Students' Self-esteem	Remarks
Family Social Stability	1265	1.00	0.786	High Predictive Value
Students' Self-esteem	1265	0.786	1.00	

Results in Table 2 showed that Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of 0.786 was obtained. This coefficient is between 0.61 and 0.80 showing a high predictive value. This means that there is a high positive predictive value of family

social stability on students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone.

Research Question Three. What is the predictive value of family relationship stability on the self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone?

Table 3: Pearson (r) correlation analysis of the predictive value of family relationship stability on the self-esteem of secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Variables	N	Family_Relationship_Stability	Students' Self-esteem	Remarks
Family Relationship Stability	1265	1.00	0.710	High Predictive Value
Students' Self-esteem	1265	0.710	1.00	

Results in Table 3 showed that Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of 0.710 was obtained. This coefficient is between 0.61 and 0.80 showing a high predictive value. This means that there is a high positive predictive value of family relationship stability on students' self-esteem in

public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone.

Null Hypothesis One. There is no significant predictive value of Family economic stability on the self-esteem of Public Secondary School Students in Awka Education Zone.

Table 4: Regression Analysis on test of significance for the predictive value of family economic stability on the self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	P-value	Remark
Predictor: Family Economic Stability					
	0.751	0.5640	0.564	0.000	Significant
Dependent: Students' Self-esteem					

In table 4, test of hypothesis four indicates that the p-value 0.000 was less than 0.05 level of significance (0.000 < 0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that family economic stability is not a significant predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone was rejected. This indicates that family economic stability significantly predicts students' self-esteem. Also, the regression

coefficient R = 0.751 with R² value of 0.5640 shows that family economic stability has 56.4% validity to significantly predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone Anambra State.

Null Hypothesis Two. There is no significant predictive value of family social stability on the self-esteem of Public Secondary School Students in Awka Education Zone.

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Table 5: Regression Analysis on test of significance for the predictive value of family social stability on the self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	P-value	Remark
Predictor: Family Social Stability					
	0.786	0.6177	0.618	0.000	Significant
Dependent: Students' Self-esteem					

In table 5, test of hypothesis five indicates that the p-value 0.000 was less than 0.05 level of significance (0.000 < 0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that family social stability is not a significant predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone was rejected. This indicates that family social stability significantly predicts students' self-esteem. Also, the regression coefficient R = 0.786 with R² value of 0.6177

shows that family social stability has 61.8% validity to significantly predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone Anambra State.

Null Hypothesis Three. There is no significant predictive value of family relationship stability on the self-esteem of Public Secondary School Students in Awka Education Zone.

Table 6: Regression Analysis on test of significance for the predictive value of family relationship stability on the self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	P-value	Remark
Predictor: Family Relationship Stability					
	0.710	0.5041	0.504	0.000	Significant
Dependent: Students' Self-esteem					

In table 6, test of hypothesis six indicates that the p-value 0.000 was less than 0.05 level of significance (0.000 < 0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that family relationship

stability is not a significant predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone was rejected. This indicates that family relationship stability significantly

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predicts students' self-esteem. Also, the regression coefficient $R = 0.710$ with R^2 value of 0.5041 shows that family relationship stability has 50.4% validity to significantly predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone Anambra State.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that family economic stability has a high positive predictive value on the self-esteem of students in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. This finding is an essential element especially as it cares about provision of the basic needs of the members of the family. The finding showed that students who are provided with the basic support for their education and overall well-being usually build self-esteem for pursuit of life. The high positive predictive value indicates that family economic stability contributes to students' self-esteem especially when it's consistent in providing their needed support. This finding aligned with Omori and Ajah (2019), who noted that family economic stability has a significant and positive relationship on the students. Also the study of Chike and Bob-Eze (2025), revealed a significant and positive relationship with students in child upbringing. The study suggested a comprehensive approach to address the complex issues associated with family instability among youths in Nigeria.

Further findings also indicated that family economic stability significantly predicted self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone. This means that a unit increase in families' economic stability to cater for their children predicts a unit increase to enhance the self-esteem of students from such

homes. This implies that students who are provided with all the essential items needed for life living and in school activities appear to be encouraged and confident. To sustain a family's economic stability there would be a stable income. Thus, parents should ensure a stable family income that helps to maintain their family economic stability. This finding is related to the study of Hassan (2016), who reported that family economic stability has a positive relationship with students' performance and asserted that students from stable families are more regular in school attendance and have high self-esteem among themselves. However, the study also noted that family instability has a negative influence on the students.

Another finding of this study revealed that family social stability has a high positive predictive value on the self-esteem of students in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. This means that family social stability helps to build self-esteem of the students. This finding implies that efforts of parents in striving to shape children's behaviours and attitude towards social values and acceptable norms, help to fit them in the society.

This effort contributes to enhancing the students' self-esteem. Hence, it becomes important for parents to be more concerned about the societal values, the self-comportment, and self-confidence which their children portray in order to maintain good morals and self-worth. The findings of Auyelbekova, Canevello, Zhigitbekova, Boltayeva, Khananyan, Akhtayeva and Klepikov (2025), concurred with this study, it revealed a positive relationship between students' self-esteem and socio-psychological

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factors. The findings also revealed the existence of a significant relationship between self-esteem and socio-psychological factors of the students. Problems, The study also specifically showed that students mostly have a moderate level of self-esteem.

The study also indicated that family social stability significantly predicted self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone. This means that the student's social life pattern helps them to familiarize relationships with people to enhance their interactions. Mohamed (2022), revealed that the social stability standard of the family shows significant and positive relationships with the students. The study recommended improved family social stability to support the students. This finding also implies that family social stability enables the students to integrate smoothly in respect of societal values, acceptable attitudes and behaviours. Chike and Bob-Eze (2025), also agreed with this finding on positive relationships of family social stability on the students and opined that family sociological influences affect students' relationships and self-esteem.

The finding of this study also revealed that family relationship stability has a high positive predictive value on the self-esteem of students in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. This finding is another important factor especially as it concerns the family members' relations, emotions, communication as well as psychological development which contribute to the nurturing of ones' self-esteem. The finding of a high predictive value showed that family relationship stability facilitates a closely related

parenting and supervision which transforms into positive behavioural outcomes, self-worth and self-esteem. In support of this finding, the study of Alsanea (2019), reported a significant and positive effect of family stability on relationship and personality. The findings also revealed that family relationship stability affects students' values and development of proper relative behavior. However, the finding of Hassan (2016) also noted that family relationship instability revealed a negative influence on students and recommended that families should encourage closely knitted relationships for understanding and caring. This will help to boost the self- esteem of the students. The study also showed that family relationship stability significantly predicted self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone. This means that the students who experience show of family affection within members of the family and a sense of caring interest stand firm with courage. This finding also shows that family relationship stability increases the students' confidence outside the family circle. This finding is peculiar with respondents who experienced childhood care filled with love and bonding. This finding is aligned with Omori and Ajah (2019), who reported a positive and significant relationship with family relationship stability. The study recommended that strong family ties should be encouraged in improving study habits among young adult learners. Also, parents and teachers must respond and relate with learners in ways that convey a sense of affection.

Conclusion

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Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that family stability has a high positive predictive value on self-esteem of students in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. It was also concluded that family economic stability, family social stability and family relationship stability significantly predicted self-esteem of public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

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1. Students should be supported by their parents to provide the basic needs that help them to feel satisfied and build up self-esteem.
2. Students should be groomed by their parents to imbibe behaviours and attitudes in line with societal values and acceptable norms to help increase their self-esteem.
3. Students also should be encouraged by their teachers and parents to embrace family affections and interactions that enable them to enhance their self-esteem.

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